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TOPIC:

MOBILE APPLICATION FOR GHANA RAILWAY COMPANY LIMITED (GH-
RAILWAYS) USING QUICK RESPONSE CODE (QR-CODE)

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DECLARATION

This is to declare that, the research work underlying this thesis has been carried out by the undermentioned student under the supervisor. Both student and the supervisor certify that the work documented in this thesis is the output of the research conducted by the student as part of his final year project work in partial fulfillment of the requirement of the Bachelor of Science in Information Technology Degree.

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I appreciate The Almighty God for giving me the strength and wisdom to complete my project. I would also like to thank my supervisor, Mr. Michael Asare for guiding me to complete this project. I would also like to thank my colleagues and friends who helped me and kept encouraging me to never give up. Lastly, my family, The Ansong Family, and my extended family for all their support and prayers.

ABSTRACT

Technological development has resulted in a boundary-free digital world. This development has resulted in a transaction through virtual money instead of real ones. In Ghana, Individuals who use the railway find it difficult with the manual process and the government to trace the revenue generated. This system deals with developing and implementing a smartphone application that is more effective and simple than the current manual process. The ticket will be present in the Passenger's phone in the form of a "Quick Response Code." Payment can be made through the User's account, i.e., if the User agrees to buy the ticket, then the equivalent 'amount' of the ticket will be deducted from the User's account. After Payment, the ticket is generated on the server-side, saved in the database, sent back to the User's mobile, and saved in the smartphone's memory. The information for each User is stored in a CLOUD database for security purposes.

CHAPTER ONE

GENERAL INTRODUCTION

1.0 Introduction

Transport or transport is the movement of people, animals, and goods from one place to another, or any combination thereof from one place to another. The infrastructure of transport includes highways, harbors, airways, and their associated facilities. Railways are the most cost-effective mode of transport for moving bulk cargo for long distances over land. They are suited to container traffic between ports and capitals. Despite the convenience and economic significance of rail transport, the railways in Africa carry only one percent (1.0%) of the global railway passenger traffic and two percent (2.0%) of the goods traffic (United Nations Economic Commission for Africa, 2009) (Dinye, 2012). Android is one of the apps that is evolving and there are always growing numbers of users. Everything falls behind time in the fast-forward world of technology. Therefore, technology's main motivation is to produce a product that is time- and cost-efficient. Due to insecurity at the railway station, people get to their destination without using a ticket (Khokale, Bunde, Karande, Ingale, & Ghaywat, 2018). This causes Railway Company Limited and the nation to lose. In today's modern world, crowding is a major issue at the railway station where people

gather to get a ticket at the railway station. Sometimes people are unable to buy tickets at the time of train arrival due to the heavy rush of passengers and travel on the train without tickets which reduces the national transport sector's revenue (Karthick & Velmurugan, 2012). Ghana Railway is the second larger land transportation system and is currently facing several problems. Through this proposed project, the project's approach is to make passenger travel at Ghana Railway more convenient. Using this Android Application, passengers can check weather conditions, distance to cover, and also buy a ticket.

1.1 Subject and Field of Study

The topic is under Android Programming. The research is in the field of computer science, primarily using QR-Code to generate Railway ticket reservations.

1.2 Problem Statement

The problem facing the company is that customers must buy the ticket from the counter or ask for a schedule, customers have to queue up for a long time in order to secure a ticket. Spending of money to print the paper ticket, no security features on the printed paper ticket thus when someone can use your ticket when gets missing, No proper records keeping.

1.3 Study Objectives

This section of the paper has been placed under two categories. General or Global objectives and Specific objectives.

1.3.1 Global Objectives

The general objective of this paper is to help the government trace the revenue-generating from the railway sector. Passengers to buy tickets without queueing to reduce time-wasting and to make payment through the mobile wallet.

1.3.2 Specific Objectives

1. To develop an Android Application for booking trains.
2. To notify the user after ticket reservation via email.
3. It minimizes the use of paper ticketing.
4. To provide the available mode of payment.

1.4 Background to the Study

Within the current ticketing system, the biggest challenge is how the government traces the generated revenue from the railway sector. Passengers have to stand inside the queue to buy tickets in this modern world. This planned "MOBILE APPLICATION FOR GHANA RAILWAY COMPANY LIMITED USING QR-CODE" project is to solve difficulties in the Railway Sector. The ticket can be booked with the proposed mobile application simply using a smartphone application, and ticket information is stored in the form of a QR

code. Time-based will mostly be used as a strategy to automatically delete the ticket after a specified period once the user reaches the destination. For safety purposes, each user's information is stored in a Cloud database. The user's phone must be scanned at the checkpoint of the railway station with the Checker application. To get the data back to the checker phone a request is sent to the server. In this way, the checker at the station will check the ticket.

1.5 Scope of the Study

The study would be limited to research into a mobile application for railway using QR-code, examine its usefulness and the problems associated with it, and how to generate a circulated solution to the problem.

1.6 Justification of the Study

As the world moves to paperless, so as Smart ticketing allows you to travel paperless, skip the queue at the ticket vending machine, and speed up the collection. The field of technology is becoming more advanced. Passengers and the government find it very difficult to buy a ticket and get revenue respectively because of many factors that need to be considered. Take an example of the railway department, where passengers had to queue to buy a ticket which wastes time and cost as well.

1.7 Methodology

The incremental model of software development will be used for software development. The software is developed in bits in this development method to make room for change until completion of the software.

1.8 Expected Results Of The Study And Possible Use

At the end of this study, the authentication system for smart railway mobile applications using QR-code would be made available to the public.

- i. Passengers must Register and Login with the mobile application using the correct credentials.
- ii. To buy a ticket with a mobile application.
- iii. To allow passengers to make payments with different payment modes.
- iv. Upon authorization by the app; the user is directed to the default home page termed DASHBOARD.
- v. To help railway industries to minimize any criminal activities.

1.9 Presentation Of Thesis

This study is organized as follows:

Chapter 1: In this chapter, the general introduction, statement of the problem, the background to the study, research objectives and significance of the study, the scope of the study, the definition of terms, and organization of chapters, are presented.

Chapter 2: It will involve a literature review that will review works related to the research and criticize them as well as give recommendations.

Chapter 3: This chapter covers the functioning of some existing systems and the overview of these systems. Rizzoli led us to the crystallization of the problem.

Chapter 4: The proposed application is analyzed in detail and its significance is discussed at length where context level diagrams are used to explain the proposed application more.

Chapter 5: This chapter includes algorithm and flowchart, data flow diagrams, entity-relationship diagrams, and use-case modeling of the proposed system.

Chapter 6: This chapter embraces the application's system implementation and testing.

Chapter 7: This chapter focuses on both the users of the application and the application itself. Under the user

documentation, the manual for both the user and the expert who will administer the application is developed.

Chapter 8: This chapter exposed the limitations of the study, the conclusion, and some recommendations made.

1.10 Study Work Plan

Purpose: To develop mobile applications for Railway Company Limited in Ghana to ease the problems for passengers.

PHASE 1: REVIEW FRAMEWORK

PHASE 2: PROPOSAL AND DISCUSSION OF THE SOLUTION

PHASE 3: DESIGN OF THE PROPOSAL

PHASE 4: CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Overview

This chapter provides an overview of the various studies used in the development of the GH-RAILWAYS in the android environment. It discusses the various software used and some knowledge surrounding the system.

2.2 Overview Of The Problem

People get to their destination without having a ticket. It also causes a liability to the Railway Business, due to insecurity at the train station, and then. There are two major security issues related to all the ticketing systems. One is validation, and the other is the checking of fares. There are several and different problems that occur as a result of these security issues. One such is e-payment. In the previous papers themselves, a new protocol was given to deal with these problems. This protocol is designed to provide a high level of security. Offered security but system performance. E-ticketing is one of the most common trading services because it does not require any paperwork in the transport network for e-ticketing. The digital era came with the introduction of emerging technologies. It also provided the concept of money for all trades and transactions in place of the real one. The Mobile Ticket or m-ticket then evolved. Existing Near Field Communication

(NFC) system supports the idea of virtual assets. Using this NFC technology, mobile tickets for public transport applications can be purchased, as Bidder Ceipidor explained. So, the idea of smartphones was developed and can be viewed as a ticket authentication tool utilizing a low-cost ticketing system. The convergence of android phones with a cloud environment ensures interoperability and elasticity. The cloud platform configures and remembers user information automatically and validates the tickets accordingly. Nevertheless, smartphones are plagued by a lack of phones' data storage, battery, and processing capacities. Together with Android Emulator, data can be stored with complete security to overcome this cloud-based virtual environment. Through the integration of a computer server into the mobile device, the burden and processing time can be that. The M-ticket concept was introduced with the introduction of Mobile smartphones that reduces the pressure of passengers to wait in queues to book tickets. The usage of QR codes ensures confidentiality. The GPS is used to automatically validate and delete ticket information during the required travel points. All user information is stored in encoded form in the cloud database thus ensuring constant accessibility and security. This ticket booking smartphone application can be used for any type of transport system, such as buses, railways, airways, etc. It was implemented first in airways, then on long-distance railways and lastly on buses. QR was used

for the Android railway ticket which came into being. Suburban Railway Company introduced an electronic ticketing network. The Android application known as the Suburban Railways Android Application not only uses all of the above apps but also uses another ticket-checking application. GPS is used in ticket validation. It saves huge amounts of energy. In the CLOUD database, the ticket checker holds the ticket number. In this proposed system, that concept is clearly described and implemented. In today's urban world, crowding is a big problem at the train station as people queue to get a ticket at the railway station which results in a variety of difficulties. The proposed project is to try and address some of the station's problems to overcome this problem and to increase security at the station. With this, the Mobile App develops to buy a ticket, check the route using Google Maps, and much more to solve problems for passengers without wasting time. The German transport association (RMV Rhein-Main-Verkehrsverbund) started a pilot project in 2005, where passengers could use their NFC to buy tickets via mobile phone. To obtain the cheapest ticket for the route, passengers only had to check-in / out at a bus terminal as they entered or left, based on the best price scheme. But the major problem is NFC enabled mobile phones are high cost.

In May 2012, Man Mohan Swarup, Abhiram Dwivedi, Chanchal Sonkar, Rajendra Prasad, Monark Bag, Vrijendra Singh suggested a framework

in which the Dynamic Seat Allocation (DSA) method, along with one of the wireless networking standards, find QR code processing to be of value. Their approach is to provide for reservations or allocations for fair processing in Indian Railway seats.

In January 2014, Sadaf Sheik, GayatriShinde, MayuriPotghan, TazeenShaikh launched an android application in which the ticket can be transported as a QR-code but it is difficult for the passenger to understand whether or not the ticket purchase is correct. Because the majority of people don't even know about QRCode.

In March 2014 Tushar Dongare, Akshay Babar proposed a model that offers different techniques to purchase tickets from their mobile application using Android Mobile's GPS facility so that passengers can quickly get the station's list and buy tickets quickly, but often GPS signals are not reliable due to certain signals obstacles. Finzgar, L. Trebar, M explains the introduction of a program that requires mobile phones to be used to buy tickets for online public transport. QR codes and RFID tags are used to sign up passengers at the start and finish of their journeys. Use of NFC and QR code identification in public transport electronic ticketing system.

2.2.1 Ixigo Train

Fig. 2.2

https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.ixigo.train.ixitrain&hl=en_US

Review

Ixigo Train allows seeing train timetable for all Indian rail passenger and express trains. Calculate exactly how much refund you are eligible for on ticket cancellation with the help of the Refund Calculator feature. Explore seat/berth maps to find convenient seats. Major Indian rail trains covered: Shatabdi Express, Rajdhani, Duronto Express, Garib Rath, Jan Shatabdi, Inter-city, Superfast Trains, etc.

2.2.2 Moovit

Fig. 2.3

play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.tranzmate&hl=en.

Review

Moovit is an app for real-time journey planners across transit modes, including buses, ferries, trains, etc. Users of this app get access to live maps and also view nearby stops and stations based on their current GPS location, as well as plan trips.

2.2.3 My Transit NYC Subway, Bus, Rail (MTA)

Fig.

[2.4play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.nyctrans.it&hl=en](https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.nyctrans.it&hl=en).

Review

My Transit is an application that allows users to plan their trips. It also communicates to users whether trips are going to be delayed or not. It is also reliable and safe.

2.2.4 Indian Railway

Fig. 2.5 Indian Railway

https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.indianrail.thinkapps.irctc&hl=en_US

Review

Indian railway allows you to spot your train, book train tickets, check train seat map, check PNR status, prediction, seat availability, station status, train inquiry, train platform

information, fare inquiry, railway station information, etc. You can spot where is my train (live train status), set a train alarm, and get answers to all Indian rail inquiries and information on Indian Railways & IRCTC.

2.2.5 Pak Rail

Fig. 2.6

https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.pakraillive.PakRailLive&hl=en_US

Review

Pak Rail Live is a free application for the general public which provides Real-Time train tracking of Pakistan Railways. Moreover, it provides schedule updates, estimated arrival of next stations, and pre-arrival notifications feature.

2.2.6 Taxify

Fig. 2.7 Bolt (formerly Taxify) - Apps on Google Play. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=ee.mtakso.client&hl=en>.

Review

Taxify is a ride-hailing app for ordering rides that are quick, safe, and affordable. This app allows you to pick up location even if you don't know your exact address and it also helps you rate your drivers to give feedback and help improve the service quality. Taxify is available in 25+ countries around the world.

CHAPTER THREE

CRYSTALLIZATION OF THE PROBLEM

3.1 History of the railway

This chapter gives us the historical background of the railway sector from the time of the colonial masters. The railway industry has been nearly 120 years since our British colonialists constructed the first railway lines. The colonial infrastructure made over a century ago helped shape the economic geography of Ghana. As a British colony, Ghana (then known as the Gold Coast) was developed by Europeans Europeans. At the time, railways were considered the best mode of transportation. (Ampong, 2019)

Currently, the type of system being used by Ghana Railway Company Limited is an internal counter system that is manually used in selling train tickets. The government finds it difficult to trace revenue in the railway sector. The problems facing the company are customers have to go to the counter to buy a train ticket or ask for a schedule, passengers have to queue up to secure a train ticket, no mode of payment options, and how to trace revenue since passengers use the train without paying. Good transport infrastructure is a pre-condition for a nation's economic development and poverty reduction. On the international level, shifts in economic ties brought on by globalization entail improvements in the efficiency of a country's transportation

network. According to a Doing Business report from the World Bank (2006), an effective transport system can reduce costs and comparative distances between trading partners, increase trade efficiency and maximize existing industrial investments and outputs from production.

3.2 Components And Features of the Existing System

There are several apps and systems available that work similarly to the proposed app. They include;

3.2.1 My Transit Nyc

Some components of this system include:

- Ability to schedules & real-time arrival.
- Ability to plan trips
- Alert Notifications

3.2.2 Moovit

Some components of this system include:

- The ability for Real-time alerts
- Live directions
- User's reports
- Map view

3.2.3 Indian Railway

Some components of this system include:

- Ability to locate where you book a trip.
- Ability to make payments through credit cards.
- Notification Component where trips canceled is sent to the driver of the cab.

3.3 Strength And Weakness of the Existing System

The transportation app is built to make the journey easy and fast for passengers and also help them get the nearest cab. Yet still, there are some strengths and weaknesses of this app, and below are some strengths and weaknesses of the respective systems.

3.3.1 Moovit

Moovit is an app for real-time journey planners across transit modes, including buses, ferries, trains, etc. Users of this app get access to live maps and also view nearby stops and stations based on their current GPS location, as well as plan trips.

Strength

As you travel, you can receive a "Get off" alert that tells you when it's time to exit your bus. (For those who doze off when travel, this function on the app helps you not to bypass your destination or stop point).

Weakness

This app does not work when access to data is lost. When there is a little loss of signal, the app is unable to give directions which causes some commuters to miss their ways to wherever they are going.

3.3.2 My Transit Nyc

My Transit is an application that allows users to plan their trips. It also communicates to users whether trips are going to be delayed or not. It is also reliable and safe.

Strength

This app can tell commuters whether or not their trips have been canceled and also helps users to plan their trips well. It also alerts commuters whenever there is going to be a delay or the trip has been canceled.

Weakness

This app tracks the location once you open it and does not allow you to disable it even if you want to use it just like a map. It also forces you to give your id and location to the company.

3.4 Comparative Analysis of Existing Systems

Table 3.1 comparative analysis of the existing systems

System feature	Ixigo	Moovit	Indian Railway	IRCTC	My Transit NYC	Ghana Railway Company (GH- RAILWAYS)
Booking	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Search train by name/number	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Yes
Payment module	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
Fares Break-up	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Yes
Route map	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes
Seat Availability	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes
Alert notification	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Rescheduled/canceled train	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Image Validation	No	No	No	No	No	Yes

CHAPTER FOUR

ANALYSIS OF THE PROPOSED SYSTEM

4.1 Overview of the Proposed System

This chapter presents the Functional requirement and non-functional requirements in the proposed system. It also emphasis on Algorithm, Flowchart, pseudocode, and system context level diagram.

Good transport infrastructure is a pre-condition for a nation's economic development and poverty reduction. On the international level, changes in trade relations brought on by globalization require improvements in the efficiency of a country's transportation network. According to a Doing Business report from the World Bank (2006), an effective transport system can reduce costs and comparative distances between trading partners, increase trade efficiency and maximize existing industrial investments and production outputs. The national growth and poverty reduction targets also rely heavily on an efficient transport system. People rely on transportation to bring food and fuel into their neighborhoods to get to markets, work, schools, to clinics for safety. To bring their goods to urban markets, farmers focus on transportation. Miners and manufacturers rely on transport for marketing and ports to get their inputs and/or products into. Failure to access transport and/or being too expensive may deny

people jobs and essential social exclusion services The Ghana Railway Application is a system that helps passengers locate routes leading to their different destinations, the time it takes you to make the journey, the distance, the amount involved in making the journey and it also gives notification during booking and cancellation. Railways are the most cost-effective mode of transportation for moving bulk cargo overland over long distances. They are suitable for transporting containers between ports and capital cities. Despite rail transport's convenience and economic significance, railways in Africa carry only one percent (1.0 %) of global rail passenger traffic and two percent (2.0%) of goods traffic (UN Economic Commission for Africa, 2009) (Dinye, 2012).

4.2 Functional Requirements

Functional requirements refer to the Functions, which were required before and covered in this system/ software we have developed. Mentioned below are the functions/ features of our newly developed software system:

Train Details

Customers may view the train timing at a date their name and the number of tickets.

Reservation

After checking the number of seats available the customers reserve the tickets.

Billing/Accounting

After reserving the required amount of tickets, the passenger has to pay for the amount of the booked ticket.

4.3 Non-Functional Requirements

Usability

The user must be able to utilize this application without any prior knowledge about the user interface. The interface must allow the user to work with the different features of the application within a minimum period. In case of any issues, the user must be able to find the solution by referring to the user manual.

Reliability

This application depends on the Internet and Wi-Fi connectivity. In case of loss of Internet connectivity, this application will discard the partially entered data and doesn't affect integrity.

Performance

The application will support only one instance per phone.

Supportability

The application should be compatible with any future changes in the charges levied by Railway ticket users just need to restart

their app and it may not incur any difficulties in the services booked.

Implementation

All users should be able to access E-Railway ticket Applications on their android based mobile phones supporting Wi-Fi and the internet.

Interface

The application interfaces with an online connected database which is been updated on every action performed by the end-user.

Operation

The Mobile User should be able to book his service successfully and if required terminate it.

4.4 Major Features or Components of ohe Proposed System

The major features of the proposed system include:

Qr-Code

The QR code contains all the user-related information and the booked ticket. In the user's directory, i.e. gallery, this QR code is stored. The QR code is later deleted from the application database as well as from the user's phone, after traveling from source to destination. The ticket checker can then scan this with the help of an application to check tickets.

Authorization

Comprises of various entities such as the Users, the Administrator, etc. Each entity must log in with the email and a password to grant access. These emails and passwords may result in further reservation processes that may edit, delete, insert, etc. So, e.g. User may print the ticket for their particular journey.

GPS

This service checks the current location of the user by the geo points of destination, after which the type of ticket is checked, and thus the ticket is deleted if two are single or updated if the type is a return.

E-Ticketing:

The User should select the specific source and destination the user requires. After completing certain steps, the ticket will be provided to the user. The ticket is generated via QR-code which can be stored in the database.

Database

This is a backup arrangement just in case the ticket checker is unable to scan QR Code if it damages the user's mobile display, battery failure, etc. In this case, the ticket checker must

validate directly with the admin servers using the username to collect accurate ticket details for authentication purposes.

Image Validation

Image validation is changing the way we live and interact with our society. Image identification is one of the very growing forms of validation in our society. Image validation is integrating into the GH-RAILWAYS Application for good security reasons. A photo or an image is taken alongside the passenger detail to use for two main purposes; to generate a receipt for the passenger after booking and for verification of the passenger when having the smartphone switched off due to low battery.

4.5 Advantages of the Proposed System

Comparing the reviewed app with the new one some of the advantages the proposed one has got over the existing one include:

- To generate a map system for individuals to find various locations and current locations.
- To provide the best available route in traveling.
- To calculate the cost involved, distance, and period in making a journey.
- To give the passenger the payment option.
- To use image validation for user verification.

4.6 Flowchart of the Proposed System

Fig 4.1 Flow Chart for the Proposed System

4.7 Pseudocode for the Proposed System.

STEP 1: START

STEP 2: REGISTER THE ACCOUNT

STEP 3: AUTHENTICATE

STEP 4: VALIDATE ENTRY

STEP 5: IF ACCEPTED, MOVE TO USER PORTAL

ELSE PROVIDE GENUINE CREDENTIALS.

STEP 6: ENTER THE DETAILS OF BOOKING/CANCELLATION

STEP 7: UPLOAD IMAGE TO PROCEED TO PAYMENT.

STEP 8: BOOKING IF YES, PROCEED TO MAKE PAYMENT

ELSE GO TO AN END

STEP 9: MAKE PAYMENT TO RESERVE TICKET

STEP 10: IF YES, GENERATE TICKET IN THE FORM OF QR-CODE

ELSE ENTER CORRECT PAYMENT DETAILS

STEP 11: GET TICKET NOTIFICATION VIA EMAIL

STEP 12: END

4.5 System Context Diagram of the Proposed System

Figure 4.2 System context level diagram

The system consists of two entities named; Passenger and Admin. The Passenger makes book requests whilst the system provides the passenger with destination information (amount involved). The Admin also updates information (updates the fare and train information) and the system also provides a list of booked or Passengers to the Admin/Administrator.

CHAPTER FIVE

DETAILED DESIGN OF THE PROPOSED SYSTEM

This chapter presents the Functional Processes, Algorithm, Flowchart, Data Flow Diagrams, Use Case Diagrams, Entity Relationship Diagram, Activity Diagram, UML Class Diagrams, and Sequence Diagram of the proposed system.

5.1 System Flowchart

Fig 5.1 System's Flowchart

Figure 5.1, illustrates the flow of data throughout the system. If the user doesn't have an account, the passenger needs to sign up but if the passenger exists, then the passenger needs to log in. The user credentials are verified and validated to allow access to the user portal where he/she can use the system. If the user selects "booking", he/she is allowed to enter the booking details and then take a picture or upload an image for validation at the train station. And if the user selects "Cancel booking" the fare is reduced by 30 percent ($\text{Cancellation} = 0.3 * \text{fare}$) and the user can also make inquiries.

5.2 Dfd (Level 1) Diagram

Fig 5.2 System`s DFD Diagram

Figure 5.2 illustrates the DFD (Level 1) of the system. The Passenger creates an account which then goes through a process called Create Account and then sends it to a data store called Account Details. Passengers can also access an account which then goes through a process called Account Detail and then sends to a

data store called Passenger Account. Passenger account details go through a process called Account Process. Passenger can search for train details in a process called Search Train and then make a booking that goes through a process called Make Reservation and require to make a payment that goes through a process called Make Payment and sends to a data store called Make Reservation. Passengers can check booked history which goes through a process called Booked History and then sends it to a data store called Make Reservation. Passengers can use a PR number (Passenger Record) number to cancel the booking which goes through a process called Cancellation and then send to a data store called Cancellation Details.

5.3 Activity Diagram Customer

Fig 5.3 Activity Diagram for Passenger

Figure 5.3 illustrates what passengers do in the system. The passenger Sign Up and then log in with the credentials. After

login, search availability of trains and then make a reservation. Passenger is allowed to make payment in different payment modes and then the ticket is generated to the passenger in the form of Quick Response code (QR-Code).

5.4 Sequence Diagram

Figure 5.4 System Sequence Diagram

Figure 5.4 illustrates the sequence diagram that depicts the interaction between objects in a sequential order, that is, the order in which these interactions take place.

5.5 Use Case

Figure 5.5 This diagram depicts the user's interaction with the system and shows the relationship between the user and different use cases in which the user is involved.

5.6. Class Diagram

Fig 5.6 System`s Class Diagram

The class diagram describes the structure of a system by showing the system`s classes, their attributes, methods, and the relationships among objects.

5.7. Entity Relationship Diagram

Figure 5.7 The Entity Relation diagram illustrates the logical structure of databases of the proposed system. It shows the relationship of entity sets stored in the database.

CHAPTER SIX

SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

6.0 System Implementation

This application was implemented using java and the development of this application required a combination of different dependencies to be implemented in different and specific aspects of the development of this mobile application. The IDE that was used in developing this application was Android Studio IDE, Gradle version 6.5, and android plugin version 3.6.1. The storage/database which was used for development is Firebase i.e., a NoSQL cloud-hosted database powered by Google, which stores data as JSON and synchronized in real-time to every connected client.

6.1 Hardware, Software, And Network Requirements

Minimum requirements for software and hardware required for the smooth running of this system are:

6.1.1 Hardware Requirement

- Android Device
- 2-GB RAM or more.
- 400MB disk space or more.
- Display Resolution of 1920 X 1080 or more.
- 60MB application space

6.2 Testing

Software testing can be described as the process of verifying and validating that the software or application is free of bugs, meets the technical requirements as guided by the design and development of the software, and meets the requirements of the user in a manner that is effective and efficient in handling all exceptional and boundary cases.

The aim of the software testing process is not only to find faults in existing software but also to find measures to improve the software in terms of efficiency, accuracy, and usability. It is primarily intended to measure the specification, functionality, and performance of a software program or application.

6.2.1 What was tested

Upon completion of the system development, some key features and functionalities of the system have been tested. The functionalities that have been tested are:

- Search for locations, schools, et cetera: During a search, the systems will retrieve location, schools, banks, or property listings that match the user's search query. The system does this by retrieving objects whose name contains the search query.
- Display search results: After a search is done, the system will display the search result to the user by returning the

searched items if they were found and displaying a message to the user if the searched item was not found.

6.3 Detailed Design Testing Process

Below are snapshots and a detailed explanation of the codes that perform some specific functions of this system.

6.3.1 Searching

```
@Override
public View onCreateView(LayoutInflater inflater, ViewGroup container,
    Bundle savedInstanceState) {
    // Inflate the layout for this fragment
    View root = inflater.inflate(R.layout.fragment_view_train, container, attachToRoot: false);
    searchInput = root.findViewById(R.id.search_input);
    TrainRecyclerview = root.findViewById(R.id.all_train);
    mData = new ArrayList<>();

    // Assign activity this to progress dialog.
    progressDialog = new ProgressDialog(getActivity());

    // Setting up message in Progress dialog.
    progressDialog.setMessage("Loading Data...");

    // Showing progress dialog.
    progressDialog.show();

    // Setting up Firebase image upload folder path in databaseReference.
    // The path is already defined in MainActivity.
    databaseReference = FirebaseDatabase.getInstance().getReference( path: "Trains");
    // Adding Add Value Event Listener to databaseReference.
    databaseReference.addValueEventListener(new ValueEventListener() {
        @Override
        public void onDataChange(DataSnapshot snapshot) {
            for (DataSnapshot postSnapshot : snapshot.getChildren()) {
                Train data = postSnapshot.getValue(Train.class);
                mData.add(data);
            }
        }
    });
}
```

Figure 6.3.1.1

During a search, the system will get the search query entered in the search bar and filter all objects whose name contains the search query by the Passenger or Admin.

For example, if a user types 'cargo' in the search bar, the system searches for all objects or trains that have the word 'cargo' in their name.

6.3.2 Book Train

```
public void onDataChange(@NonNull DataSnapshot dataSnapshot) {
    for (DataSnapshot snapshot : dataSnapshot.getChildren()){
        Train train = snapshot.getValue(Train.class);
        int occupie_seats = (train.getReal_avail_seats());
        int newseat = occupie_seats+1;
        rootref.child(strtrain_id).child("real_avail_seats").setValue(newseat);
        String booking_id = mdb.push().getKey();
        Book book=new Book(booking_id,booking_code, booking_status,strtrain_id, train_number, train_name, train_type, train_fare,
            train_source,train_destination, train_arrival_time, train_depature_time, person_booked,
            passenger_one_booked, passenger_two_booked,passenger_three_booked, date_booked);
        mdb.child(booking_id).setValue(book);

        progressDialog.dismiss();
        Toast.makeText(getActivity(), "Train Booked Successfully", Toast.LENGTH_SHORT).show();
        Fragment frag = new HomeFragment();
        Fragment frag = new QrCodeTicketFragment();
        final Bundle qrangs = new Bundle();
        qrangs.putString("ticket_id",booking_code);
        qrangs.putString("ticket_date",date_booked);
        qrangs.putString("booked_person",person_booked);
        qrangs.putString("ticket_png1",passenger_one_booked);
        qrangs.putString("ticket_png2",passenger_two_booked);
        qrangs.putString("ticket_png3",passenger_three_booked);
        qrangs.putString("ticket_source",train_source);
        qrangs.putString("ticket_dest",train_destination);
        qrangs.putString("ticket_arrival",train_arrival_time);
        qrangs.putString("ticket_departure",train_depature_time);
        qrangs.putString("ticket_status",booking_status);
        qrangs.putString("ticket_fare",train_fare);
        qrangs.putString("ticket_nam",train_name);
        qrangs.putString("ticket_num",train_number);
    }
}
```

Figure 6.3.2.1

Train reservation or booking is done by both the Passenger and Admin. When a particular train is searched and the 'BOOK NOW' is clicked, the user is required to upload an image before the user is allowed to proceed. Extra three persons can be added and proceed to make the payment and then the QR-CODE generation.

6.3.3 Add Train

```
public void addtrain() {
    train_name = trainname.getText().toString();
    train_number = trainnumber.getText().toString();
    train_source = trainsource.getText().toString();
    train_dest = traindestination.getText().toString();
    train_depart_time = traindeparture.getText().toString();
    train_arrival_time = trainarrival.getText().toString();
    available_seats = seats.getText().toString();
    working_days = workingdays.getText().toString();
    unitprice = price.getText().toString();
    alreadybookedseats=trainseatsavailable.getText().toString();
    train_descript = traindescription.getText().toString();
    flag = 0;
    if (trainname.getText().toString().trim().length() == 0) {
        trainname.setError("Train name cannot be Empty");
        trainname.requestFocus();
        flag = 1;
    }
    if (trainnumber.getText().toString().trim().length() == 0) {
        trainnumber.setError("Train number cannot be Empty");
        trainnumber.requestFocus();
        flag = 1;
    }
    if (trainsource.getText().toString().trim().length() == 0) {
        trainsource.setError("Source cannot be Empty");
        trainsource.requestFocus();
        flag = 1;
    }
    if (traindestination.getText().toString().trim().length() == 0) {
        traindestination.setError("Destination cannot be Empty");
        traindestination.requestFocus();
        flag = 1;
    }
}
```

Figure 3.3.1

To add train is only done by the admin, the admin fills in the input boxes with the required details or information. When the admin clicks the submit button, the train details will be stored in the database for retrieval, updating, or deletion.

6.4 Test Cases

Table 6.4.1 - Test cases implemented

S/N	WHAT IS TO BE TESTED	EXPECTED RESULT	WHITE BOX OR BLACK BOX	TEST RESULT
1	Search Train	Searching for a train.	Black-box	Pass
2	Book Ticket	Make train reservation.	Black-box	Pass
3	Fare Enquiry	Enquire for fare in a journey.	Black-box	Pass
4	Network accessibility and inaccessibility	To connect to wi-fi or mobile data.	Black-box	Pass
5	QR-Code Generation	To generate Qr-code for users.	Black-box	Pass

CHAPTER SEVEN

SYSTEM DOCUMENTATION

This chapter presents the user manual for the system. The chapter also provides texts and images on how to use the various components of the system.

7.1 User Manual for the system

Application Startup

To start the GH-RAILWAYS application, follow the steps given below:

1. Click on the GHR icon on the application menu.
2. On clicking the GHR icon, the application starts and displays Intro-screen. The intro screen contains the following options:
 - a. Swipeable screens brief you on what the app is about.
 - b. Continue Button to proceed
 - c. An option to skip the swipeable screen.

Fig 7.1.1 Intro-Screen 1 on launching the app

Fig 7.1.2 Intro-Screen 2 on launching the app

2 Registration and login

To register with the GH-RAILWAYS application, follow the steps given below:

- 1 Start the GH-RAILWAYS application; click Sign-up on the Intro Screen to register an account to use the app.
- 2 After account registration, the Login page is displayed anytime the user visits the app by clicking on Sign-in on the Intro-Screen.
- 3 Enter your credentials for authentication.
- 4 After authentication, you are then logged into the app and ready to use it.

The screenshot shows a mobile application interface for account registration. At the top, there is a dark blue header with a white icon of a person in a suit and a lightbulb, and a button labeled "CLICK TO UPLOAD IMAGE". Below this, the form contains several input fields: "FULL NAME", "PHONE NUMBER", "USERNAME", "EMAIL", "Address", "PASSWORD", and "CONFIRM PASSWORD". At the bottom of the form is a large, rounded blue button labeled "SIGN UP". The status bar at the top of the phone shows the time as 12:31.

Fig 7.2.1 Account registration.

Fig 7.2.2 Login page.

3 User Dashboard

Fig 7.3.1 Passenger dashboard.

Fig 7.3.2 Admin dashboard.

The dashboard is where you can find a profile, and other privileges to the application but in Fig 7.3.2 (Admin dashboard), the admin has all the privileges the passenger has and extra privilege to the app. The Admin can add train, train station, and dashboard items of the GH-RAILWAYS app.

4 Make Reservation (Ticket Booking)

Fig 7.4.1 Reservation page.

Ticket reservations could be done by both the Admin and Passenger. Image upload is necessary if not, the user cannot proceed to the next page.

CHAPTER EIGHT

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

8.1 Conclusion

This project was developed using the Android Studio IDE and java as the main programming language. This mobile application enables railway users (Passengers) to book a ticket with a smartphone's help. This Android application minimizes the manual work of both ticket bookers and ticket-checkers. With this latest application, a major problem of issuing local train tickets can be solved as no one has to wait in queues and the headache of carrying the ticket is also avoided. This app also saves a large amount of work for ticket checkers. Also, it moves from the manual ticket checking system to the automated ticket checking process by simply scanning the ticket validation QR code.

8.2 Challenges faced during System Implementation

The main challenges faced during the implementation of this application are that reliable internet connectivity is required all the time. Automatic exterminate of generating tickets after a specified interval of time, i.e., after completing the journey for which ticket is generated. Facilitate secure and smooth mode of payment options and Maintain the cancellation and refund policy for generated tickets. This project has helped me gain more knowledge and brought out the development skills in me.

8.3 Recommendation and Future Works

In this project, more advancement modification can be done using GPS (Global Positioning System) to get the current location of the train by fitting the GPS device in the train, to get the location of the user from where the user entered the train which will be beneficial for checker and also to validate or delete the ticket according to the source point and destination point of the user. For station level security we can provide the hardware devices on the respective stations to validate QR Code of the user before the user enters or leaves the station. If the QR Code is valid by the hardware device then he will get access to the platform. We can also add one the feature that is when a user enters a source and destination point and if the user gets down in the middle of the journey then the GPS should track user location and then with respect to his remaining journey, the remaining amount should be added to the user account.

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